

THE MANUFACTURE AND TESTING OF 3D MULTILAYER WOVEN I-BEAMS

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SUMMARY: Composite I-beams were manufactured from E-glass and vinyl ester resin. The glass preforms for the I-beams were produced using advanced multilayer weaving techniques and consolidation of these preforms was carried out via Vacuum Assisted Resin Injection (VARI). The design requirements for the beams were based upon those for a cross-member in a typical footbridge. Three- and four-point tests demonstrated that the composite beams achieved the required structural performance except for a 5% reduction in expected bending stiffness. This was thought to be due to a reduction in the anticipated flange thickness. The use of multilayer woven preforms also demonstrated improved manufacturability of the beams when compared to standard 2D glass fabric.

KEYWORDS: FRP I-beam, multilayer weaving, mechanical performance, vacuum assisted resin injection

INTRODUCTION

For most of their existence, modern-day composite materials have been intimately related to the aerospace industry. Their high specific strength and stiffness have made them the material of choice for an increasing number of aerospace components and it is only relatively recently that composite materials have begun to be used as major structural components in civil engineering projects. Although the mechanical performance and corrosion resistance of composites have always been of interest to civil engineers, the high cost of raw materials and labour intensive production methods have limited their use.

Increasingly, however, it is becoming apparent that as the cost of materials is reduced and improved manufacturing processes are developed a potentially huge market for composites is forming in the construction industry. In the USA alone, the problems associated with ageing infrastructure is costing the economy billions of dollars annually with recent estimates stating that around 230,000 of the 575,000 bridges in the US are either structurally deficient or functionally obsolete [1].

Composites can be used in a number ways to overcome the infrastructure problems currently facing the USA and many other countries. They have the potential to help repair existing problems [2] through techniques such as wrapping of concrete support columns [3], which is particularly relevant in earthquake-prone areas, and strengthening of concrete beams with

bonded composite plates [4,5]. Composite materials have also been used in the manufacture of a number of pedestrian and road bridges, including those at Aberfeldy (Scotland) [6], Stroud, Gloucestershire (UK) [6] and Russell, Kansas (USA) [7]. To date, hundreds of composite footbridges have been manufactured, with the choice of composite materials being made for reasons which include; ease of construction and maintenance, corrosion resistance, nearly inaccessible locations, environmental concerns and aesthetics. In particular, one major factor for the choice of composites in footbridges is the desire to reduce the overall weight of the bridge as this is a substantial proportion of the total load.

As mentioned earlier, the use of composites in large civil engineering projects has been limited by the high material costs and the labour-intensive methods required for composite component production. With the advent of relatively low-cost, commercially available, large carbon fibre tows the problem of high material cost is beginning to be addressed, however, forming these tows into the required shapes is still a matter of concern. Pultrusion [8] is a method of producing composite structural components in the large volumes that are needed in civil engineering and has certainly been an important technique used in the production of most of the composite bridges currently standing. The supply of fibre in the pultrusion process is generally in the form of individual tows or two dimensional woven fabric. This can result in a costly set-up stage for large components, due to the large number of fibre sources that need to be fed into the equipment to build up the final component. Utilising advanced textile manufacturing processes it is possible to produce a single fibre preform in the desired structural configuration. These techniques have been shown to produce components with improved performance at a reduced cost [9].

This paper reports on initial work, conducted at the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures, which investigated the potential of using advanced weaving techniques to produce three-dimensional fibre preforms for composite I-beams.

DESIGN OF I-BEAM

Performance Requirements

There are numerous applications for I-beams within the civil engineering field, each of which will dictate their own particular performance requirements upon the structural member. For the purpose of this investigation a specific use for the I-beam had to be determined in order that dimensions and mechanical properties could be calculated. Due to the increasing use of composite materials in footbridges it was decided to design the beams as generic cross-members in such an application.

The generic footbridge structure consists of two longitudinal beams upon which the cross-members are placed with the bridge deck on top of these cross-members (Fig. 1). The load on the bridge is the weight of the people times a safety factor plus the dead weight of the bridge structure itself. For this investigation it was assumed that the width of the bridge was 2 metres with the longitudinal supporting beams placed 1 metre apart. Standard design requirements stipulate a maximum of 9 people, each weighing 100 kg will fit in a square metre. This gives a uniformly distributed load on the bridge of 8.8×10^{-3} MPa. If a safety factor of three is applied this becomes 30×10^{-3} MPa, which also allows for approximately 120 kg/m^2 of structural weight. It was assumed that the deck will distribute the load evenly to the cross-members, therefore reducing the bridge design to a two-dimensional problem of a simply

supported beam with a distributed load. If the distance between the cross-members is taken to be 1 metre a distributed load on each cross-member of 30 N/mm is obtained.

Fig. 1: Illustration of generic footbridge used for design of I-beams

With these dimensions and calculated loads, simple beam theory gives the maximum bending moment and shear load in the cross-members as 3.75 kNm and 18.75 kN respectively. The bending stiffness of the beam is determined by the maximum allowable deflection of the bridge deck, which is limited to $1/80^{\text{th}}$ of the deck width. This restriction yields a required minimal bending stiffness of $EI = 4.69 \times 10^{10} \text{ Nmm}^2$ for the beam. With these performance parameters in mind a multilayer woven preform was then designed for use as the I-beam.

Weave Architecture

For this investigation the materials for the I-beam were chosen on the basis of their cost and ease of use. The cost of E-glass is substantially lower than the higher performance carbon fibres and is less susceptible to damage during the weaving process than carbon. Vinyl ester was chosen as the resin material as it is relatively cheap and cures at room temperature thus removing the need for expensive curing cycles and high temperature tool materials.

The preforms were woven at the CRC-ACS on a doobby hand loom (for initial trials) and an advanced electronic jacquard loom (for the production of full size preforms). The use of these looms restricted the manufacture and style of the preform in a number of ways. Firstly, the majority of weaving looms are incapable of producing material with fibres in the $\pm 45^\circ$ direction as well as the normal 0° and 90° directions. It is possible to manufacture material with fibres in all 4 directions on special looms but this material is not widely available. This restriction of only 0° and 90° fibres in the web and flanges will result in having to increase the thickness of the web in order to obtain the required shear strength. It would be possible to add additional material to the web at $\pm 45^\circ$ but for the purpose of this investigation the design was restricted to only multilayer 0/90 fabric.

Due to the set-up of the looms, which were also being used for the manufacture of preforms for other investigations, there were restrictions placed upon the types of preforms that could be produced. This meant that the weave architecture had to be, essentially, identical in the web and the flange even though the performance requirements for both areas are very different. Thus, for the purpose of this initial work, the selection of weave architecture was based upon previous work performed at the CRC-ACS which examined critical factors in the manufacturability and weave architecture of multilayer woven preforms [10]. This selected weave architecture contained fibre distributions of 54% and 46% for the longitudinal (along the length of the beam) and transverse direction respectively with the total fibre volume

fraction of the beam predicted to be 50%. It should be noted that in commercial production of preforms for composite I-beams, a loom would be initially set-up to produce the required material as a single preform with optimised weave architectures for both the flange and web.

Dimensions of I-beam

The I-beam contains four independent dimensional variables, namely; the web height (H), the flange width (W), the web thickness (t_w) and the flange thickness (t_f). These dimensions will be determined by the performance requirements of the beam and the mechanical properties of the materials used.

The Young's moduli of E-glass fibres and vinyl ester are 72 GPa and 3.4 GPa respectively. For a composite containing a 54% - 46% distribution of fibres in the longitudinal - transverse directions and a 50% final fibre volume fraction the estimated Young's moduli [11] in the longitudinal and transverse direction are;

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= 25.6 \text{ GPa} \\ E_2 &= 23.4 \text{ GPa} \end{aligned}$$

In order to adequately determine the beam dimensions shear tests were performed upon the multilayer woven composite. These tests produced the following mechanical properties;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Maximum Shear Stress} \quad \tau_{\max} &= 40 \text{ MPa} \\ \text{Shear modulus,} \quad G_{12} &= 4.5 \text{ GPa} \end{aligned}$$

The web area of the beam was calculated from the maximum shear load capacity required by the beam (18.75 kN) and the maximum shear stress that the multilayer woven composite material will be allowed to carry. This allowable shear stress was set to be 30 MPa, giving a safety factor of 1.3. Using this data, the web area was given by the relation;

$$Area_{web} = \frac{ShearLoad}{\tau_{average}} \quad (1)$$

which yielded a required web area of 625 mm^2 .

For the bending properties of the I-beam it is desirable to place the flanges as far apart as possible, but increasing this distance decreases the web thickness and increases the chance of the web becoming unstable in lateral/torsional buckling. With this in mind and also taking into account the range of preform dimensions that could be produced on the loom, the web height and thickness were chosen to be 102 mm and 6.1 mm respectively.

The minimum moment of inertia of the beam is dictated by the required bending properties. The required bending stiffness depends directly on the moment of inertia. With a predicted Young's modulus of 25.6 GPa in the longitudinal direction of the multilayer woven composite, the stiffness requirements demand a minimum moment of inertia of;

$$I_{yy} = \frac{EI}{E_1} = 1.8 \times 10^6 \text{ mm}^4 \quad (2)$$

The required bending moment capacity is linked to the moment of inertia via the following relation;

$$\sigma_x = \frac{M \cdot z}{I_{yy}} \quad (3)$$

where σ_x is the maximum allowable stress in the longitudinal direction and z is the level where this stress acts (this stress will occur at the outer flange surfaces). Previous tests upon the multilayer woven composite had measured the minimum strength of the material to be 320 MPa in tension. Applying a safety factor of 1.3 the maximum allowable stress in the flanges was assumed to be 250 MPa. From Eqn. 3 this results in a minimum moment of inertia of approximately $7.7 \times 10^5 \text{ mm}^4$. Comparing the two values obtained for the moment of inertia shows that the bending stiffness requirement is the major factor in dictating the minimum moment of inertia and thus the flange area as well. The moment of inertia can be expressed in terms of beam dimensions,

$$I_{yy} = \frac{1}{12} \cdot \left[W \cdot H^3 - (W - t_w) \cdot (H - 2 \cdot t_f)^3 \right] \quad (4)$$

Substitution of the known parameters leads to the following relation between the flange thickness and width.

$$t_f = 51 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sqrt[3]{\frac{W \cdot 102^3 - 12 \cdot 1.8 \times 10^6}{W - 6.1}} \quad (5)$$

The flange width and thickness were chosen to prevent flange buckling at the design loads and to conform with the range of preforms that could be produced by the loom. A buckling analysis of the flange lead to the selection of a flange width of 62 mm and a flange thickness of 4.8 mm. The required dimensions of the I-beam were therefore;

Web height (H) = 102 mm

Flange width (W) = 62 mm

Web thickness (t_w) = 6.1 mm

Flange thickness (t_f) = 4.8 mm

MANUFACTURE OF I-BEAM

Weaving of preforms

Initial weaving trials were conducted upon a 24 shaft dobby hand loom and the resultant preforms produced were used to manufacture specimens for three-point bend tests. These tests were conducted to determine whether the weave architecture and dimensions of the web, that was based upon earlier rail-shear tests, would in fact provide adequate shear strength.

Full scale specimens for 4-point bend tests were manufactured upon an automated, electronically controlled, jacquard loom. This loom was used not only because it could produce samples of the required size but also to demonstrate the manufacture of advanced textile preforms, that are suitable for composite structures, on an industry standard production loom.

As mentioned earlier, the decision to use these two looms restricted the manufacture of preforms in a number of ways. One important restriction was that it was not possible to manufacture the I-beam as a single preform with the loom set-up that was in operation at that time. The looms could have been reset in order to produce a single preform but this would have been a time-consuming and very costly process. Therefore, in the interests of speed and cost reduction, the I-beam was manufactured as 2 preforms that were consolidated as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Illustration of preform consolidation

Fig. 3: Example of an idealised multilayer weave architecture

Due to the fact that two looms were used in the production of specimens, there were some slight differences in the preforms produced. In the samples from the dobby handloom the longitudinal and transverse yarns in the multilayer structure were essentially uncrimped. The various layers of yarns were kept in place by a low percentage of a very fine E-glass yarn that travelled in the preform thickness direction, binding the yarn layers together and providing the preform with adequate handling characteristics. It is expected that this binder yarn will not significantly contribute to the in-plane mechanical performance of the I-beam. An idealised representation of this type of weave architecture is shown in Fig. 3 and the proportions of the various yarn types in the final composite I-beam is listed in Table 1. The preforms produced by jacquard loom differ slightly from this in that they do not have a separate binder yarn holding the layers together, this job is done by a small percentage of the transverse yarns. This difference resulted in a more rapid production rate than using a different binder yarn but produced an architecture in which the longitudinal and transverse yarns were slightly crimped. It is thought that this crimping may lead to a small reduction in the stiffness of the I-beam.

Table 1 again lists the proportions of yarns in the final composite I-beam for the jacquard preforms.

Table 1: Details of critical I-beam dimensions, fibre proportions and overall composite fibre volume fractions

Loom	I-beam Dimensions H, t _w , W, t _f (mm)	Longitudinal (%)	Transverse (%)	Binder (%)	Fibre vol. frac. (%)
Dobby	99, 6.0, 62, 3.9	56.4	41.2	2.4	51
Jacquard	99, 6.3, 62, 4.2	55.8	44.2	-	52

Consolidation

The preforms manufactured by both loom types were consolidated with vinyl ester resin by a process known as Vacuum Assisted Resin Injection (VARI). Generally, this process relies on drawing resin through the preform by applying vacuum at one end with a resin reservoir at the other end (Fig. 4). Unlike resin transfer moulding techniques, where resin flow between inlet ports and outlets is primarily through the preform itself, in the VARI method the primary resin flow is through a carrier which distributes the resin over the surface of the preform after which the secondary flow is through the preform thickness. The resin therefore has less distance to travel through the preform and thus resin injection pressures do not need to be as high. These factors generally allow cheaper, more easily managed tooling to be used thus saving on production costs. One disadvantage is that a smooth tool surface on the finished component is not possible on the surface that was in contact with the carrier material, although this was not a critical consideration for this work.

Fig. 4: Illustration of the Vacuum Assisted Resin Injection technique

The VARI tooling set-up for the I-beams is illustrated in Fig. 5. This tooling was enclosed in a vacuum bag, which was necessary for the VARI process to work and also compacted the preforms to achieve the required fibre volume fractions. It was found that the best results were obtained when the carrier material was placed next to the flanges. The fillet space at the junction of the C-channels and the flanges was filled with uniaxial E-glass yarn to prevent premature failure at this point. I-beams produced with this arrangement were found to be free of voids with dimensions and fibre volume fractions very similar to the design values (Table 1) although the flange thicknesses were less than the design values due to the restrictions placed by the set-up of the loom. The small differences in thickness between the two preform types was thought to be due to the slight changes in preform architecture and fibre volume fraction.

Initial trials with the tooling were conducted with standard 2D glass fabric. It was found that cutting to size and accurately maintaining the position of the large number of fabric layers required for the I-beams was very complicated and time-consuming and occasionally lead to defects in the consolidated beams. The use of the multilayer woven preforms significantly decreased the time required for the setting up of the preform in the tooling by more than 50%. This demonstrates the potential advantages that can be gained in the production of complex-shaped components by the use of multilayer preforms that are woven to the required shape.

Fig. 5: Illustration of the tooling used for consolidation of the I-beams

TESTING OF I-BEAM

Shear Tests

Three preforms produced on the dobby handloom were consolidated into I-beams and tested in three point bend to determine the maximum shear load capacity of the weave architecture and beam dimensions selected during the design phase. Table 1 lists the dimensions of the I-beam cross-section whilst the test span used was 370 mm. To ensure failure of the web via shear, wooden blocks were placed inside the I-section on the points where the load was introduced to reinforce these areas and to prevent premature failure of the beam. These blocks were of the same timber used for the tooling and were glued into place using vinyl ester resin of the same composition as the resin in the beam.

Measurements of load and neutral axis displacement were made throughout the tests and the failure load was used to calculate the shear load capacity of the I-beam. Table 2 shows the experimentally measured shear load capacity (average of all three beams) compared with the shear load required by the design conditions. The results show that the weave architecture and dimensions chosen for the I-beam can adequately accommodate the maximum shear load required by the original design. The measured average shear load of the beams (23.5 kN) gives a shear strength for the composite material of 37.6 MPa, which is a very similar result to the strength obtained earlier by rail shear tests.

Bend Tests

The automatic jacquard loom was used to produce three I-beam preforms which were consolidated and tested in four-point bending in a pure bending rig [12] to determine their bending stiffness and bending moment capacity. Table 1 lists the dimensions of the I-beam cross-section whilst the inner and outer spans of the test rig were 678 mm and 1292 mm respectively. In a similar fashion to the previous three-point bend tests, wooden blocks were glued inside the I-section of the beam to provide reinforcement at the loading points and thus ensure failure of the beam within the inner span.

Table 2 again shows the results of the tests (average of all three beams) and compares them with the design requirements. It is clear that the I-beams have a more than adequate bending moment capacity, almost twice that required. However, the flange dimensions, which control the beam's moment of inertia, were selected to just satisfy the required minimum bending stiffness calculated during the design phase. The experimental results for bending stiffness were found to be approximately 5% less than the design requirements. This shortfall is thought to be due to the actual thickness of the flange being less than the design value. This difference would lower the bending stiffness of the I-beam below the design requirements.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of I-beams

	Design	Experimental
Shear Load Capacity (kN)	18.75	23.5 ± 2
Bending Stiffness (10 ¹⁰ Nmm ²)	4.69	4.47 ± 0.2
Bending Moment Capacity (kNm)	3.75	7.32 ± 0.7

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The test results presented in the preceding section show that the I-beam manufactured by advanced weaving and liquid moulding techniques successfully achieved the majority of its design requirements. The one exception was a slightly lower bending stiffness that was thought to have resulted from a reduction in the flange thickness. It should be noted that due to the restrictions placed upon the beam design by the available looms, this design was far from optimised for its end use as a footbridge cross-member. The addition of ±45° fibres to the web area to improve its shear performance would have allowed a reduction in the web cross-section and thus the weight of the beam. Similarly, if the initial set-up of the loom had allowed a variation in the weave architecture between the flange and the web, a higher proportion of longitudinal fibres could have been placed in the flange thus improving the beam's bending performance. The placement of higher modulus carbon fibres in the flange would also have improved the bending performance of the I-beam whilst at the same time allowing a reduction in the weight of the beam.

Initial trials in utilising the VARI method to manufacture the I-beams had demonstrated the difficulty of maintaining accurate positioning of the large number of layers of standard 2D glass fabric required for the beams. The use of a smaller number of fabric pieces (multilayer woven preforms) was observed to lead to a significant improvement in manufacturability. An optimal loom set-up would have allowed the preform to be manufactured as a single piece of

multilayer fabric which would help reduce the set-up costs inherent in production methods, such as pultrusion.

It is therefore clear that advanced weaving techniques, coupled with improved processes for resin infiltration, have the ability to manufacture composite structural components to specified design requirements. The use of multilayer weaving also demonstrated the potential advantages that could be gained by processes such as pultrusion by using single preforms that have been woven to the required shape.

REFERENCES

1. "Cable news...", *Advanced Materials News*, Millbank, P., Ed., No. 82, April 1996, pp 1-8.
2. McConnell, V. P., "Can composites rebuild America's infrastructure?", *Advanced Composites*, November/December 1992, pp. 22-31.
3. Brooks, N., "GRP wraps up bridge repairs", *Reinforced Plastics*, July/August 1995, pp 30-32.
4. Zou, R. D., Jones, R., Hanna, S., Lam, Y. C., "An investigation on strengthening of concrete beam with GFRP laminates", *First Australasian Congress on Applied Mechanics*, Melbourne, Australia, 21-23 February, 1996, Vol 1, Grzebieta, R., Wong, A., Marco, J., Lam, Y., Eds., pp 461-466.
5. Weaver, A., "Carbon plate stops the cracks", *Reinforced Plastics*, July/August 1995, pp 34-37.
6. Weaver, A., "Hybrid bridges exploit composites durability", *Reinforced Plastics*, July/August 1995, pp 24-29.
7. *Composite News: Infrastructure*, No. 59, 16 December, 1996, Loud, S., Ed. Composites Worldwide, Inc., 1996, pp 6-8.
8. Strong, A. B., "Versatility in pultrusion", *Composites Fabrication*, June 1996, pp 9-13.
9. Müller, J., "The extension of advanced composites into the machine industry", *4th International Conference on Automated Composites*, Nottingham, UK, September 6-7, 1995, The Institute of Materials, pp 499-509.
10. Bannister, M., Herszberg, I., Nicolaidis, A., Coman, F., Leong, K.H., "The manufacture of glass/epoxy composites with multilayer woven architectures", *to be published in Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*.
11. Halpin, J., Tsai, S., "Effects of environmental factors on composite materials", *AFML-TR67-423*, June 1969.
12. Cimpoeru, S., "The modelling of the collapse during roll-over of bus frames consisting of square thin-walled tubes" *Ph.D. thesis*, Monash University, Melbourne, Australia, December, 1992.